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THE EFFECT OF SIGN LANGUAGE TO LEARNERS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS OR LSENS' RECALL OF COLOR WORDS IN BALAKILONG INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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RESEARCH ABSTRACT

Sign Language was hypothesized to increase student recall of color words. Three data sources were used to determine Learners with Special Education needs' recall of color words with the support of using multisensory approach (1) flashcard method, (2) color word assessment sheet, and (3) sign language survey. Data sources supported the use of sign language to increase student recall of color words. Flashcard method results that two LSENS showed slight growth and one LSEN showed significant growth. After the researcher analyzed the color word assessment sheet, he observed growth for all three LSENS. A Likert survey was utilized to determine parents' input and the survey indicated that sign language is beneficial to LSENS' recall of color words. The three data sources collectively indicated sign language increased LSENS' recall of color words. The researcher had utilized the lesson plan which can be proposed and recommended to other SPED teacher targeting the recall of color words incorporated with sign language. An important point to remember when considering the results of this study is the good effect of multisensory approach and several repetitions of the same concept in order to gain mastery of skills.

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